

Spectrophotometric estimation of aceclofenac in tablets

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Abstract : A new simple, precise, highly specific and economical spectrophotometric method for the determination of aceclofenac in its pharmaceutical dosage forms has been developed. The method is based on the formation of a coloured complex of the drug with ferric nitrate in acidic medium, which has absorption maximum at 470 nm. Beer's law is obeyed over concentration range of 75–200 µg/ml. The result of analysis for the method has been validated statistically and by recovery studies.

Keywords : Spectrophotometry, aceclofenac.

Aceclofenac, {2-[(2,6-dichlorophenyl)amino]benzene acetic acid carboxy methyl ester}¹ is used as analgesic and anti-inflammatory agent². In the present communication, a simple colorimetric method is being reported for the estimation of aceclofenac in tablets, the only form in which it is marketed. The proposed method is based on the formation of reddish orange coloured complex between the drug and Fe³⁺ in the presence of hydrochloric acid with absorption maxima at 470 nm.

Results and discussion

The presence of amino group in aceclofenac enabled the formation of reddish orange coloured complex with ferric ion which is present in the ferric nitrate under the acidic condition, exhibiting λ_{\max} at 470 nm. In this method Beer's law was obeyed in the concentration range of 75–200 µg/ml. Chemical reaction of the complex is given in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

The optical characteristics are : Beer's law limits (75–200), absorption maxima (470 nm), molar absorptivity ($795.1 \pm 5.3 \text{ L M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$), Sandell's sensitivity ($0.4454 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}/0.001$ absorbance unit), correlation coefficient (r) (0.9917), slope (m) (9×10^{-4}), and intercept (c) (0.1662). The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity show that the method is sensitive. The optimum conditions for colour development has been established by varying the different parameters involved. The proposed method was applied for the analysis of drug in tablets and compared with the UV method (λ_{\max} 275 nm) (Table 1). The results of analysis of commercial formulations significantly showed low values for standard deviation, show the precision of the method. It is concluded that the results of analysis are in good agreement for each tablet. To evaluate the validity and reproducibility, pure drug was added to the previously analyzed pharmaceutical preparations and the mixtures were analyzed by the proposed method. The percentage recoveries are given in Table 1. The percentage recovery was close to 100%. This study revealed that the common excipients and other additives such as lactose, starch, gelatin, talc and magnesium stearate, that are usually present in the tablet dosage forms do not interfere in the analysis. The method is best suited for small manufacturing houses equipped with colorimeters.

The reproducibility, repeatability and accuracy of this method was found to be good, which is evidenced by low standard deviation. Thus it can be concluded that the method developed in the present investigation is simple, sensitive, accurate and precise. Hence this can be suc-

Table 1. Estimation of aceclofenac in pharmaceutical formulations

Sample	Labelled amount in (mg/tab)	Amount obtained	Amount	%Recovery \pm S.D. ^a Proposed method
		(mg) \pm S.D. ^a Proposed method	obtained (mg) \pm S.D. ^a UV method	
1	100	99.87 \pm 0.64	99.60 \pm 0.57	100.15 \pm 0.83
2	100	99.63 \pm 0.71	99.62 \pm 0.59	101.05 \pm 0.28

^aAverage of six determinations.

cessfully applied in the estimation of aceclofenac in tablets.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

A GBC cintra 10 UV/VIS spectrophotometer with 10 mm matched quartz cells was used in the present study. The chemicals used were of analytical grade. Ferric nitrate (Merck) (4% w/v) was made in mixture HCl (1 N), methanol and distilled water (2 : 2 : 6). The commercially available tablets of aceclofenac were procured from local market. Aceclofenac (analyzed sample) as provided by Aristo Pharma Pvt. Ltd. was used as such without further purification.

A solution of aceclofenac was prepared by dissolving 100 mg of standard aceclofenac in 100 ml of methanol and suitably diluted to get a working standard solution of 1000 μ g/ml. Aliquots (0.75, 1, 1.25 ... 2 ml) of working standard solution were transferred into a series of 10 ml volumetric flasks. Solution of ferric nitrate was (2.0 ml) added. The volumetric flasks were kept on boiling water bath for 30 min. The volumes were made up after cooling with methanol. The absorbance of the reddish orange chromogen was measured at 470 nm against reagent blank and the calibration curve plotted.

Average weight of twenty tablets was determined and

these were then finely powdered (separately for each of the two formulations tested). The powdered amount equivalent to 100 mg (accurately weighed) was extracted quantitatively with (4 \times 20 ml) of methanol, insoluble excipients were separated by filtration. The supernatant liquid was transferred to 100 ml volumetric flask and the volume made up. One ml of the solution was taken in a 10 ml volumetric flask and proceeded as above. The concentration of the drug was determined by using the calibration curve plotted as above. The concentration of the drug was then calculated.

The results of the above method were compared with the results obtained using UV method with ethanol as solvent.

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